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Abstract	D4.8 contains the implementation and description of two tools created for the ACTION project: an infographic to have a general and aggregated overview on pilots information, and a tool to create dedicated dashboards for pilots
Keywords	Dashboard, infographic, data collection, data representation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

D4.8 contains the description of the two dashboards implemented in the ACTION project.

The first is a live infographic to provide a general and aggregated data overview of the ACTION pilots and the citizen scientists involved. This document contains the methodology used, the evaluation of the dimensions, the implementation, and first considerations on the data collected so far (referring to the editing time of the present deliverable).

This document presents also the second dashboard tool, available for any Citizen Science project interested in visualizing time-series data, with an example of implementation for a specific pilot.

Both the instruments are available: the first is on the ACTION website, for everyone interested in the ACTION project, pilots and results; the second is planned to be used directly by pilots, to implement dedicated dashboards.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The ACTION project supports many different pilots, both the resident ones and the ones involved in the two open calls. To improve data representation, two dashboards were created with different purposes. The need to represent in a timely, clear and reusable way the information collection by the pilots, as a general summary of the main contents and description of citizen scientists involvement, is fulfilled with two live dashboards. The first is a tool to describe grouped and anonymized data like the target impacts, types of pollution addressed, SGDs covered, dissemination activities, citizen scientists enrolled, data gathered, and geographical distribution of the activities. It is a project-wide tool supporting the accelerator.

The second tool gives any pilot the possibility to create their own specific dashboard to represent their time-series data. It can be useful not only for dissemination purposes, but also to help the activity of the citizen scientists involved.

This document is divided in two main sections, one for each tool, with a final chapter presenting the conclusions.

2 LIVE DASHBOARD

This chapter describes the activities done to create the ACTION live dashboard, added to the official website¹, able to summarize the most relevant information of the pilots involved in the ACTION project. Starting from the methodology used to create and manage this tool, the following paragraphs then describe the selection of the data collected, the analysis, the further refinements, the implementation, and how the update process is organized.

2.1 Method

The purpose of the live dashboard is to provide a set of intuitive, easy-to-use online widgets for different types of indicators (from socio-economic information to data on actively participating citizens) and project progresses (e.g. number of data records gathered and validated, publication, events, etc.). As each pilot is different (everyone is free to operate independently), the information to be collected and represented is presented at a high level. Furthermore, as pilots are at various stages, the request for information is done at specific moments (e.g. the end of the accelerator period), to guarantee that most of them provide as much available data as possible (also considering that Covid-19 restrictions caused a slowdown in activities in most pilots). Finally, for the internal pilots, the respective coordinators provided the information, for external pilots, data was directly inserted by mentors.

2.2 Dimensions evaluation

Since several different types of information can be collected to describe each pilot, initially we performed an analysis of the available data and the potentially interesting angles to have a broad and comprehensive picture. We started from the comments and suggestions we received during the first project reviewer, in which the recommendation was made to make the pilot information more prominent and clear.

We then discussed within the consortium, especially with the leader of the accelerator on the one hand and with the leader of the impact assessment on the other hand. This activity was aimed at understanding the already available information as well as the potential aspects that could be integrated in an interactive visualization. The outcome of this activity was a list of dimensions to be filled in for each pilot (as explained in the following). We decided to take a pragmatic approach, including all those aspects for which we were confident to get data from at least a subset of the pilots and discarding the dimensions that we already understood to be hard to collect.

To simplify the data collection process, a shared excel file was set up, containing a table with a column for each parameter that needs to be gathered. In this table, a row is assigned to each pilot to fill in the available information, stating also the names of the pilot leader, the pilot mentor and the

¹ <https://actionproject.eu/>

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person responsible for compiling the table. Finally, to keep track of the update status of all the rows, a cell is reserved for the date of the last update.

2.2.1 Dimensions and subdimensions

To better organize the gathered data, four main dimensions were established, namely “Project Characteristics”, “Demographics of participants”, “Quantifiable Achievements”, and “Impact”. Each of them was then given a set of subdimensions, which are the exact data that are needed to create the live dashboard.

To begin with, the “Project Characteristics” dimension aims at providing the link between the pilots and the citizens they involve. This is done by firstly gathering information about the amount of projects that are already open to additional contributions from citizens, to then investigate more about their activities. The pilots are asked to provide data about their geographical reach (i.e., where citizens activities are carried out), the type of pollution addressed and which activities they ask the citizens to perform. The data regarding this last point is mapped on the categories detailed in the “ACTION Participatory Lifecycle”, which is part of the toolkit² that all pilots are provided with.

Secondly, the self-explanatory “Demographics of participants” dimension aims at detailing the gender and age distribution, the nationalities and main languages, the education levels, the diversity among participants, and the income level of the citizens involved with the pilots. In particular, diversity among participants is referred to cultural background and mother tongue.

The “Quantifiable Achievements” dimension is intended to show the progress that the pilots have made. This includes both “material” data, like the production of specific assets or the organization of events, as well as the involvement of the citizens in their activities and their public outreach. To be more specific, these achievements are divided as follows:

- Number of active citizen scientists
- Number of x produced or analyzed (where x can be a data point, dataset, photo, etc.)
- Number of events organized
- Number of persons reached (via events, social media)
- Number of scientific publications (articles, chapter, book)
- Number of scientific outputs (different from papers)
- Number of non-scientific publications (blog post, press releases)

Finally, the “Impact” dimension is established to profile the operation field of the different pilots. This is done by investigating two parameters: the area of impact and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)³. For the former, the pilots are asked to state in which areas their work is expected to have (or already having) an impact (e.g. Social or Economic impact, cf. deliverable D6.1). The latter sub-dimension concerns the aforementioned Sustainable Development Goals, or Global Goals, which are a collection of interconnected goals set in 2015 by the United Nations Assembly that are meant to be achieved by 2030.

The 17 SDGs are:

² <https://actionproject.eu/toolkit/>

³ <https://sdgs.un.org/>

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- 1) No Poverty
- 2) Zero Hunger
- 3) Good Health and Well-being
- 4) Quality Education
- 5) Gender Equality
- 6) Clean Water and Sanitation
- 7) Affordable and Clean Energy
- 8) Decent Work and Economic Growth
- 9) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
- 10) Reducing Inequality
- 11) Sustainable Cities and Communities
- 12) Responsible Consumption and Production
- 13) Climate Action
- 14) Life Below Water
- 15) Life On Land
- 16) Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions
- 17) Partnerships for the Goals

Notably, each of these goals has several targets and various progress indicators. Some of the pilots were able to report specific information about which of these targets they were actively tackling, but, due to most of the projects not being able to reach this accuracy level, the infographic only displays the pilots active on each major SDG.

2.2.2 Refinements

As stated before, each pilot is free to operate independently and, for that reason, there is a limit to how precise the gatherable data can be. After the first collection of information from the pilots, it was clear that some of the subdimensions had to be cut out of the live dashboard due to this lack of information.

More in detail, the omitted subdimensions are:

1. Nationalities
2. Educational level
3. Mother tongue
4. Income level
5. Diversity among participants

For nationality and mother tongue the information was mostly given, but they were very generic (e.g., mainly Norwegian but also English, Persian, Estonian, Greek, Vietnamese, Polish) and not easy to be grouped or quantified (no specific information on the number of citizen scientists involved for each language). Educational level and diversity among participants, even if they represent a really interesting information, are omitted because in one case data are collected only

for a couple of pilots for the moment, and in the other case the percentage is not meaningful. For the income level, as it is quite sensitive data, the information is missing for all the pilots.

2.2 Implementation

The live dashboard implementation is divided in the selection of the most appropriate tool based on the considered requirements, the presentation of the dashboard, implemented as an infographic, and the methodology to update data in the future.

2.2.1 Tool selection

When choosing the appropriate way to implement the dashboard, several requirements were taken into consideration. First and foremost, the tool of choice must be available in a free-to-use version. Secondly, the created dashboard or infographic has to be embeddable in the project website and not only visualizable from the tool's website. The used platform must also allow the import of external data through either external ".csv" files or a Google Sheet document. Finally, this tool needs to allow a sufficient level of customizable features, to stylize the output and match the style of the webpage it is embedded into.

After evaluating several instruments, the tool of choice was *Infogram*⁴. It is available in a free version but forces the user to make the charts and the data publicly available on their website, a condition that was acceptable in our case. In its free version, Infogram also offers different embedding options, either fixed or responsive. These alternatives include the possibility of adding the output to the HTML in a fixed `<iframe>` element, in a responsive `<div>` element, with the option of making it load asynchronously, or to embed it in WordPress by adding a custom-made code or downloading the related plugin. The appearance of the result is also customizable, allowing the user to change the colors and fonts used, and to add external assets.

The toolkit also supports several data input methods, even if some are available only to paying customers. In the free version, the user can import Excel, Google Sheets, or CSV files, with the only limitation being that the file needs to be manually re-imported to update the charts.

When choosing the best way to visualize the information, the available options were either a dashboard or an infographic. While the first could include a more accurate set of charts, it also might require a more complete and accurate dataset and could be harder to read for a person external to the ACTION project, which this particular dashboard would be targeted to. By choosing an infographic, this lack of detail of the data can be partially solved by graphically narrating a story that fills the gaps for the target audience, with the end-goal of helping the users understand how to read the charts and the progress made by the pilots over the duration of the project.

⁴ <https://infogram.com/>

2.2.2 Infographic presentation

We worked with the support of a communication designer from Cefriel, in order to design the overall “storytelling” of the live dashboard. Starting from the information collected in our spreadsheet, taking into consideration the available information and also reflecting on the questions and curiosities a website visitor could have with respect to the displayed information, we came up with the following information organization. It is worth noting also that the visual appearance of the dashboard was also discussed several times with the entire project team and different iterations led to the result illustrated hereafter. Since, as explained before, we could not collect all information from all pilots because of their difference, the infographic represents the available data and in some cases it discards some details that were available only for a very limited set of pilots.

In the selected infographic representation, the “card” style adopted is mirroring the ACTION official website’s style and colors, to seamlessly embed the infographic in a custom page on said website.

At the beginning, the focus and subject of the infographic are the pilots, and all the charts regard their achievement and operations. These charts are computed on the data pertaining to the “Project Characteristics” and “Impact” dimensions, with some mentions of specific assets produced by the pilots. By showing how many projects are working with external citizens, the focus and subject of the infographic switches from the pilots to the actual citizens. The information shown here concerns the assets gathered or produced by external citizens rather than the pilots themselves, the people involved in specific tasks, and, finally, the data collected in the “Demographics of participants” dimension.

As previously mentioned, the initial focus of the graphic is on the pilots, reported in Figure 1, showing the total number of active projects, their focus, and their field of work. The tiles on the right show the number of pilots per “pollution type”, while the following bar chart highlights the relevance of the identified areas of impact. This is computed by aggregating the data that expresses, on a scale from 1 to 5, how relevant every area is for each pilot, with the chart also showing the distribution of these evaluations. On the left, the graphics show the available data about the public reach of the pilots and the assets produced, divided into “scientific publications”, “articles/blog posts”, “posters”, and “press releases”.

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Active Pilots

36725+ People reached

21 Events organized

500+ participants

12 Scientific output

3 Press releases

45 Articles/Blog posts

Figure 1: Infographic section on pilots

The remaining impact sub-dimension, concerning the Sustainable Development Goals, is visualized with a series of tiles, as shown in Figure 2, that presents the icons and colors assigned to the goals from the United Nations on their official website. The bottom part of the tiles then presents the total number of pilots that are expecting to have an impact on that specific goal, with the same project being again able to appear in more than one goal.

Figure 2: SDGs coverage

The storyline of the infographic then changes, switching from being pilot-centric to focusing on the citizens, external to the projects, that are involved and active on one or more tasks. To introduce this shift, the infographic sets up a divider that creates space and clearly separates the top from the bottom section. This divider, shown here in Figure 3, visualizes the percentage of pilots that are already collaborating with external citizens, outside their initial target group.

After introducing this subject change, the infographic mimics the initial section with the data regarding the citizens. On the left, it presents the totality of the people that actively participated in some of the pilot’s tasks, also reporting the number of data gathered grouped by type.

Next to it, the chart displays which tasks the citizens are currently performing, and in which measure. At the time of writing this deliverable, we do not have precise numbers on how many citizens are performing each task, so the number shown concerns the number of pilots that are currently active on said tasks.

This data is represented mimicking the ACTION Participatory Lifecycle, copying the layout and colors to recall the origin of the different tasks.

40% of our pilots already open to additional contributions from citizens

660+

Active Citizens

Figure 3: Infographic on active citizens

The last part of the infographic (Figure 4) displays the information gathered for the “Demographics of participants” dimension. While the data is partial and cannot be considered an accurate representation of the demographics of all the active citizen scientists, the available information about age, gender is visualized with two donut charts. The choice of the range for age was made by optimizing the information received from the pilots, who used different methods of classifications: in some cases the ages were divided in ten categories, while in others only one global range was appointed, or even “any age”. Finally, the areas where the pilots are operating is listed with the flags of the covered countries, and a small map of the world for those pilots active

worldwide. A link to each pilot page also serves as a means to allow website visitors to seamlessly navigate from the live dashboard to the more detailed information of each pilot.

Figure 4: Infographic on active citizens demographic and pilot locations

2.2.3 Future data collection procedure

As previously mentioned, the data gathered for this infographic is not complete and its coverage varies greatly among the different pilots, with some managing to provide information down to the smallest detail, while others only able to fill in a broad overview of their activities.

Since this is a live infographic that gets updated regularly to include the latest information about the pilots and the citizens involved, there are some improvements that will be implemented in the data gathering process to improve the details and representation of the end result. These concern both the structure of the shared file in which the information is collected, and the time the actors are required to fill in said data.

To begin with, some of the sub-dimensions listed previously will be improved by adding additional information regarding how and in which format the data should be provided. Regarding the “Demographics of participants”, data for the “Mother tongue” and “Nationalities” sub-dimensions will need to include either the numbers or the percentages of the citizens to be able to properly represent the two distributions. For a similar purpose, the data about the participant’s “Income level” and “Education level” will be forced into predefined ranges that will prevent the pilots from inserting differently distributed information that might not be mergeable without a loss of accuracy.

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Still, in case of missing or very partial information on those dimensions, we will keep avoiding their display also in the future releases of the dashboard.

Finally, following the same logic, the “Areas of impact” and the “Assets produced” will be also provided with two closed sets with the categories in which the information should be divided into, which should help in standardizing the data format and in visualizing the results.

The second part of this optimization process concerns the scheduled moments in which the pilots are supposed to enter the updated information. In the first round of the accelerator, the data to populate the infographic was collected mostly at the end of the period. This choice was due to different reasons: some pilots only enrolled participants during the accelerator process (they were not already active at the beginning), the analysis of the data to be asked was ongoing, and the pilots were already involved in many activities, and the pandemic situation made other interactions with the pilots more pressing than collecting the dashboard data. For the second round, as the structure to collect information is already optimized, the schedule to align the infographic contents is synchronized with the agenda of the accelerator. Starting from the 1st of March, when the process will start, each month there will be an “Interim call update” where a general statement of the pilots is given. On these occasions they will be asked to provide potential new information that will then be added to the infographic. Pilots will know this schedule in advance, to be able to provide faster feedback. Below, the scheduling with specific dates is reported:

Dates	Events
01/03/2021	First data collection for new pilots/update for resident pilots
07/04/2021	Update of data collection
05/05/2021	Update of data collection
02/06/2021	Update of data collection
30/06/2021	Last update of data collection

Pilots mentors will be in charge to report the updates in the templates provided for data collection.

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2.3 Discussion

At the time of writing of this deliverable, the information collected in the infographic shows that most of the pilots are related to light and soil pollution (four and three out of ten), as shown in Figure 1. Thirty events were organized, and more than 850 persons were reached so far. The most expected impacts are the social and the environmental ones, while the others are less covered (e.g., economic impact is expected only in three out of ten pilots). However, this distribution is in line with the expectations for the ACTION pilots, due to the nature of the open call targets. The dissemination activity is mostly on articles or blog posts (with a total amount of 22), even if also posters are used (7 publications). For the SDGs, the infographic (Figure 2) presents only the 7 goals addressed, where 7 pilots are focused on good health and well-being, 6 on sustainable cities and communities, 5 on quality education and responsible consumption and production. Also, clean water and sanitation, climate action, and gender equality are addressed, but with lower numbers (two pilots for each goal, while only one for the last goal).

As far as the active citizen information is concerned (Figure 4), out of x pilots that provided this information, there are more than 340 volunteers now, most of them males (60% males vs 40% females), with the highest percentage of people being under 30 y/o. This is probably due to the involvement of high schools in the activities, which is stronger in some pilots, and lack of data from the other pilots that are missing accurate information on these topics. In Figure 3 it is also possible to see also the huge number of data gathered, especially audio files, images, sampling, and datasets. Furthermore, from the ACTION Participatory Lifecycle, it is possible to observe that most of the activities executed by the citizen scientists are related to data collection and data analysis, which is aligned with the purpose of the pilots.

3 TOOL FOR CREATING DASHBOARDS FOR PILOTS

This section is going to present the tool deployed on the ACTION servers that allows pilots to create dashboards easily. Also, it will describe the experience carried out by one of the pilots. We identified this need, since several pilots make use of different kinds of sensors that continuously collect data, which form time-series. The visualization of those data is important, both for the pilot organizers who want to monitor their project and for the citizen scientists themselves who want to “see” how they are contributing to the citizen science initiative.

3.1 Tool: Grafana

To build dashboards different requirements need to be considered: 1) A database to store data generated by the pilots and 2) a tool to easily develop dashboards on time-series data. For the latter, the search was oriented towards a tool where users don’t need programming skills and where the platform can be hosted on the project servers.

Following these requirements, the tool chosen to implement the dashboard is Grafana⁵.

Figure 5: Dashboard example

Grafana is an open source platform to build dashboards, designed to visualize time series data. It contains interesting features such as:

- **Visualization plugins.** Grafana allows users to use a diverse collection of charts (bar charts, pies, histograms, etc ...) to represent temporal data. These plugins (or panels) can be added to the dashboards simply by dragging the component to a whiteboard. Also, they can be customized by modifying colors, line style, legends, title, formats, etc.

⁵ <https://grafana.com/>

- **Alert system.** Users can create alerts to warn about specific changes in the dataset or on the variables used. These alerts can be sent to users through different notification channels such as email, Telegram, etc.
- **Unify.** Grafana has a collection of plugins to access a plethora of data sources. It includes popular databases such as MySQL, Postgres or Influxdb and other kinds of sources such as APIs, JSON files, etc. This is very relevant because the panels (or graphs) are not subject to the data sources, it means the same panel can use different data sources. Grafana has also developed a wizard to facilitate the access to the data without SQL knowledge (see Figure 6).
- **Open.** It is an open source platform that one can deploy in his own servers. Also, it is possible to use the services provided by Grafana Cloud.
- **Extend.** Grafana has hundreds of plugins to extend its functionality and to build predefined dashboards.
- **Collaborate.** Grafana allows managers to create different teams of users and to restrict their access to different resources of the platform (dashboards and data). Also, organizations can be created. In the ACTION project, the platform was set up with different organizations based on pilots, establishing the appropriate permissions to access the resources.
- **Share.** Panels and dashboards can be shared with a URI. This implies that it can be embedded in websites extending their dissemination.

Figure 6: SQL wizard

3.2 Use case: Noise Maps

A webinar was organized to teach pilots the use of this tool and its possibilities. The pilots were shown how to create/select panels (charts), organize them in dashboards and include them on webpages. Slides are available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068095>

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Next, the experience with one of the pilots is reported. Noise Maps allows citizens to generate and analyse urban sound data, empowering communities to take action to reduce unwanted noise and protect the local sonic heritage.

An example of the dataset generated in the project NoiseMaps is visible here⁶. The following fields are worth highlighting:

- Identifier of the device
- Data
- Time
- Point of interest (location)
- Complexity
 - Dissonance
 - Dynamic Complexity
 - HFC
 - Spectral Complexity
- Sound Pressure Level: is the deviation from the ambient caused by a sound wave.
- Loudness: is the **subjective** perception of sound pressure.
- Noise Sources: identified by an algorithm developed in the project.
 - Air conditioner
 - Car horn
 - Children playing
 - Dog bark
 - Drilling
 - Engine activation
 - Jackhammer
 - Siren
 - Street music

This data was cleaned and indexed in an Influxdb database, which is especially designed for storing time series data. There is a specific plugin in Grafana to connect it to this kind of database.

First, the dashboard was designed (meaning the panels to show on it). Figure 7 shows the result.

Different panels are visible in this dashboard.

- **Description.** It is a panel to write a description of the location. It can be filled in with markdown or HTML text.

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4059533>

- **Sound pressure and Loudness.** These panels are represented by different line charts to show the different levels of the variables.

Figure 7: Carme square dashboard

- The **Complexity Variables** panel shows different variables on the same chart. This data is obtained from the database with the SQL assistant (Figure 8). This is an example of how easy it is to access the data and to represent multiple variables.

Figure 8: Data access assistant

- Finally, a bar chart representing the **probability** (0 .. 1) of detecting different noise sources is presented. Figure 9 shows how to customize this panel. It is possible to change the orientation and the colours of the bars depending on the value of the variable. It is also possible to define the minimum and maximum values as well as the number of decimals to show.

Figure 9: Bar chart

Once the dashboard was implemented, it was important to define the time period covered and how to modify it. This is done using the calendar placed on the top of the dashboard. Note that the users (even the anonymous ones) can change this value without interfering with the visualization of other users. Also, the manager can activate the refresh parameter to refresh automatically the dashboards, without reloading the webpage.

In the case of Noise Maps, the pilot team is also interested in embedding the dashboards in a geographical platform where the users can access the data related to a specific location by pressing a point on a map. For doing that, it is necessary to include each panel in the needed location using the url generated by Grafana. It can be done through the share option panel (see Figure 10). It is also possible to see the HTML code needed to show the panel.

Figure 10: Share panel option

The final result of the map (shown in Figure 11) with the panels embedded can be accessed on Instamaps⁷.

Once the first location-based dashboard had been generated, it was very easy to replicate it. The JSON file, which describes the dashboard, can be copied and re-imported to create a new visualization. It is important to change the location parameter in the SQL assistant to access the corresponding data. This operation can be done through the API of Grafana too.

⁷

<https://www.instamaps.cat/visor.html?businessid=831377c9bdddea84446422c028506ecd&3D=false#16/41.3808/2.1692>

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Figure 11: Final result of the panels in Instamap platform

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4 CONCLUSIONS

The work described in this deliverable will be carried out also during the rest of the ACTION project lifetime, involving the new pilots enrolled in the second round of the accelerator, with a continuous update of the information gathered, and the support in the creation of personalized dashboards. As expected, the information collection highlighted the diversities among the pilots, the challenges to overcome when representing this kind of information, and the need for a pilot to have a dedicated dashboard.

Another version of the deliverable will be submitted in M36 (D4.9 Live dashboard and media publishing portal 2) with a general update of the data representation for the infographic, the analysis of the data collected at the end of the project, and the new experiences on personalized dashboards for pilots.